

Dehydrogenation performance of Mg-based hydride composite ($Mg_{90}Ti_{10}+5wt. \% \text{ graphite}$) from metal hydride containers equipped with basin-like extended surfaces

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Mg-based hydrides have gained formidable interest for hydrogen storage applications due to their high intrinsic hydrogen capacity of up to 7.6 wt%. However, their ability to absorb/desorb hydrogen is limited by their slow inherent kinetics and the heat and mass transfer within the storage container. The dehydrogenation of the container becomes important when coupling with a fuel cell since the fuel cell requires a constant H_2 flow rate to provide continuous power output [1]. In this study, we investigate numerically the dehydrogenation performance of a cylindrical container (See Figure 1) filled with 300 g of $Mg_{90}Ti_{10}+5wt\% \text{ C}$ nanocomposite, with the objective to identify the operating conditions at which the H_2 flow rate is higher or equal to the threshold for the proper functioning of a solid oxide fuel cell. The nanocomposite was prepared by high-energy reactive ball milling in H_2 [2]. The experimental results from the H_2 ab/desorption cycling of the container demonstrated that the composite absorbs an average of 5.5 wt.% of hydrogen [3].

Figure 1: Physical and computational model

The heat and mass transfer inside the container is modeled using the commercial software package COMSOL. The heat transfer characteristics are calibrated with the experimental data extracted from a recent study [3]. The dehydrogenation performance was studied under different operating H₂ pressures and initial temperatures. Figures 2 and 3 show the temperature and reacted fraction spatial distribution, respectively.

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of bed temperature

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of desorbed hydrogen fraction.

Under given heat transfer features, the results showed the overall dehydrogenation kinetics of the container allows for a constant supply of H₂ to a fuel cell with different power ratings from 100 to 250 W for an extended period.

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